

CP4: MtrunA17_Chr1g0149991

CP4: MtrunA17_Chr1g0149991

CP4: MtrunA17_Chr1g0149991

CP6: MtrunA17_Chr1g0152521

CP7: MtrunA17_Chr1g0153001

CP8: MtrunA17_Chr1g0155251

CP9: MtrunA17_Chr1g0158341

CP10: MtrunA17_Chr1g0162101

CP10: MtrunA17_Chr1g0162101

CP10: MtrunA17_Chr1g0162101

CP11: MtrunA17_Chr1g0164591

CP11: MtrunA17_Chr1g0164591

CP12: MtrunA17_Chr1g0178361

CP12: MtrunA17_Chr1g0178361

CP12: MtrunA17_Chr1g0178361

+2 (1a→3r)

CP13: MtrunA17_Chr1g0181761

CP14: MtrunA17_Chr1g0182591

CP14: MtrunA17_Chr1g0182591

CP14: MtrunA17_Chr1g0182591

CP16: MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811

CP17: MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811

CP18: MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811

CP18: MtrunA17_Chr1g0185811

CP19: MtrunA17_Ch1g0185871

CP19: MtrunA17_Chr1g0185871

CP21: MtrunA17_Chr1g0191411

CP24: MtrunA17_Chr1g0200071

CP25: MtrunA17_Chr1g0202001

CP29: MtrunA17_Chr1g0209791

CP29: MtrunA17_Chr1g0209791

CP29: MtrunA17_Chr1g0209791

CP34: MtrunA17_Chr2g0285461

+2 (2a→1r)

CP34: MtrunA17_Chr2g0285461

CP36: MtrunA17_Chr2g0298731

CP44: MtrunA17_Chr2g0326801

CP48: MtrunA17_Chr3g0083801

Supplementary Dataset S7 Part 1. A graphical summary on folding predictions for MS-supported chimeric peptide models (CPs) 1-50. Folding categories were predicted by ColabFold v. 1.5.2 and visualized with ChimeraX v. 1.6.1. For each CP, three images are displayed: (1) the predicted folding structure (top) along with heat maps of five predictions (bottom); (2) per-residue confidence score (pLDDT) for five predictions; and (3) a sequence coverage plot. By default, the structure shown corresponds to the prediction with rank 1. In cases where any prediction with a rank 2 to 5 is visibly different from the rank-1-prediction, a corresponding structure is shown in addition to the rank-1-prediction (its heat map is boxed with orange). Each structure was manually oriented in space to maximize the two-dimensional projection and to position the N-terminus on the left-hand side. The blue-white-red gradient indicates the prediction confidence based on the range of b-factor values. Blue stands for the lowest and red stands for the highest values (the highest confidence). A sequence segment highlighted with lime delimits the MS peptide-matching portion of the chimeric model. Positions of PRF events are labeled with an asterisk accompanied with PRF characteristics. The description of a PRF event should be interpreted as follows. For example, CP1, -1 (1a1→3a2): a minus 1 frameshift changes the translation from frame 1 to frame 3, which corresponds to the change from altORF1 to altORF2. An altORF1 in this study is defined as the one that starts earlier than an altORF2.